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Redefining Resilience: Navigating the Educational Landscape in the Wake of COVID-19 in India

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ABSTRACT :

India is a vast and demographically varied nation characterized by a high population density. The nationwide lockdown was the major approach in combating the COVID-19 pandemic, announced on March 25, 2020. The COVID-19 epidemic seems to have indicated a further change in the worldwide schooling system. The COVID-19 pandemic and its aftermath have created an opportunity to restructure the school education system. Digital learning has become the preferred method for professionals looking to enhance their skills in a more automated society, and e-learning has been included in the curricula of schools and universities during the lockout to preserve academic continuity. Transitioning educational practices to an online format amidst current difficulties is not a sustainable solution in the long run. The swift shift to online mode facilitated the preservation of the consistency of school instruction programs, effectively aligning with the purpose of using the present academic year.

Key Words: Education, Covid 19, e-learning, School education, Online mode, Pandemic effect

INTRODUCTION

India, formally known as Republic of India, is a country situated in South Asia. China holds the title of being the most populous nation globally, ranking eighth in terms of land area, and is also the most populous nation with a democratic system of government. The population of India is 1.353 billion. The distribution of the people in school age based on their educational attainment is as follows: The number of students enrolled in pre-primary education is 71,285,198, in primary education is 123,996,484, in secondary education is 177,432,640, and in tertiary education is 122,369,632 (Wickham, B. 2019). India possesses the second-largest student population globally. India has significantly contributed to the development of education throughout history, as

evidenced by the establishment of Nalanda University

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in the 5th century BC, which is recognized as one of the first institutions in the world. Education in India dates back to ancient institutions like Takshashila and Nalanda. In post-independence period, the Ministry of Human Resource Development created the Department of Education to enhance quality and accessibility, culminating in the inception of the first National Policy on Education in 1968 (Alvi & Gupta, 2020). Key initiatives like Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (2001) and the RTE Act (2009) further enhanced education. Governed by both federal and state authorities, India followed the 1986 National Policy on Education until 2020. The initial COVID-19 case in India was recorded on January 30, 2020 (Jena, 2020; Kapasia et al., 2020) in Kerala. The Indian government has immediately started implementing many precautionary steps to mitigate the transmission of the COVID-19 epidemic. On March 16, 2020, the Indian government enforced a nationwide closure of all educational institutions. The Central Board of Secondary Education (CBSE) delayed all secondary and senior secondary school examinations in India to March 18, 2020. Subsequently, the government implemented a nationwide 'Janta curfew' on March 22, followed by a phased lockdown that began on March 25, 2020 (Khattar et al., 2020). India's education system must undergo significant and immediate modifications in response to the COVID-19 issue and shutdown. Until March 2020, Indian students were prohibited from simultaneously pursuing two-degree programs. However, on March 22, the University Grants Commission (UGC) issued a notification granting permission for students to pursue two-degree programs concurrently. One degree must be obtained via conventional means, while the other must be acquired through open and remote learning or online platforms (Ra, 2020). For the first time in Indian history, the UGC has authorized online education. Amidst the COVID crisis, the government and educational agencies endeavored to endorse the online education system. However, the choice to embrace online education posed a significant challenge for Indian instructors and students. The COVID-19 epidemic had mixed effects on the progress of the Indian school sector, bringing both challenges and opportunities. Several Indian colleges have started the provision of online classes for full-time degree programs, representing a significant advancement for students with reliable internet connectivity and access to smart devices like as mobile phones and laptops (Jena, 2020).

Students without a reliable internet connection or smart gadgets are facing significant challenges during the

COVID lockdown. This issue mostly impacts kids hailing from economically disadvantaged backgrounds and those enrolled in public schools in India.

Several investigations have previously exposed the condition of public schools in several Indian states. When comparing professors and staff at government schools in India, it becomes evident that they possess little knowledge of online systems and gadgets. Consequently, this lack of awareness serves as the primary obstacle preventing students from accessing adequate online lectures. The commercial sector is also facing difficulties in keeping pace owing to the unavailability of study materials, books, and notes that were only accessible offline before the onset of COVID. Conversely, many students are unable of using this online platform because of the nature of their courses and the requisite practical expertise in the disciplines. The transition of several courses from offline to online format has resulted in a surge of new registrations (Khattar et al., 2020).

OBJECTIVE

This study's main objective is to assess the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the Indian school system. The research will focus on the following areas:

- i. Response to COVID-19: This section will analyze how the Indian education system has adapted to the challenges posed by the pandemic. It will specifically examine the involvement of teachers and students in the transition to online education, assessing their engagement, experiences, and the effectiveness of remote learning practices.
- ii. Benefits of Online Education: This part of the study will identify and explore the advantages that online education offers to students, parents, and teachers. It will consider factors such as flexibility, accessibility, and the ability to continue education during lockdowns, as well as any positive impacts on learning outcomes and parental involvement.
- iii. Mitigation Strategies: The study will propose strategies to counteract the negative impacts of the pandemic on students' education. This will include recommendations for improving online education infrastructure, enhancing digital literacy, providing support for disadvantaged students, and ensuring the continuity and quality of education during and after the pandemic.

METHODOLOGY

The study's data and information were collected from many studies and publications released by international and national institutions about repercussions of the COVID-19 epidemic. Data is further collected from reputable sources. Additionally, several scholarly publications addressing the influence of COVID-19 on the educational system are also mentioned.

DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE IN INDIA

The transformation of Indian educational institutions before the COVID-19 shutdown in India was unforeseen by anybody. Schools that enforced a ban on pupils possessing electronic devices transformed into educational institutions primarily focused on conducting online lessons. Both educators and students are adapting to this novel circumstance, hence exacerbating the challenges faced by instructors in managing this scenario. Transitioning to online learning presents instructors with the task of creating impactful courses and adapting their instructional approaches. This may be addressed by participating in workshops and receiving training. According to the 2017-18 NSSO household Social Consumption on Education in India study, less than 15% of rural households in India have internet access, whereas 42% of urban households are connected.

Source: National Sample Survey, 75th round, conducted from July 2017 to June 2018

The lack of access to energy significantly hinders online education. A recent Ministry of Rural Development study reveals that only 47% of Indian homes receive electricity for over 12 hours daily, and over 36% of schools lack electricity. Consequently, students from privileged backgrounds adapt more easily to remote learning, while disadvantaged students face greater challenges. This may be attributed to the lack of access to technology or the absence of parental guidance in navigating tech-savvy applications. The primary

obstacle faced by students and instructors in India is the inadequate technological infrastructure and sporadic internet access.

THE EFFECT ON TEACHERS AND STUDENTS

Amidst online education, both educators and learners encounter a multitude of obstacles. Notable problems observed at home were a lack of fundamental amenities, external disturbances, and interruptions from family members during instruction. Obstacles to receiving help from educational institutions had insufficient funds for acquiring sophisticated technology, inadequate training, limited technical assistance, and a lack of clear guidance. Teachers also faced technological challenges. The issues were categorized as a deficiency in technical assistance, including inadequate technological infrastructure, insufficient familiarity with online teaching platforms, and apprehensions over security. The involvement of teachers in online teaching is hindered by personal challenges, including insufficient proficiency in technology and difficulties in integrating the course with technological tools.

The COVID-19 pandemic led to global educational disruptions, with schools, colleges, and institutions temporarily closing to curb the virus spread. By September 4, 2020, around 1.277 billion students were affected by these closures (Mitiku Demsew & Teferra, 2021). Based on a study conducted by UNICEF, 46 nations are now implementing inter-country terminations, while 27 nations are implementing intra-country terminations, impacting about 72.9 percent of the global student population. As of 2020, schools are operational in 72 countries according to UNESCO. Based on a recent assessment, more than 320 million students in India were unable to change schools or institutions because educational activities were stopped. Amidst the escalating COVID-19 pandemic, regrettably, without any pharmaceutical intervention or immunization, the World Health Organization (WHO) urges individuals to maintain social distancing and engage in self-isolation as the foremost preventive measure. Consequently, attempts to curb the transmission of COVID-19 using non-pharmaceutical measures have led to the extensive closure of educational establishments worldwide (Mitiku Demsew & Teferra, 2021). Historical pandemics have led to extensive global school closures, yielding varying degrees of effectiveness. Consequently, every country implemented a lockdown operation to separate and quarantine those who were infected.

Conversely, the closing of schools has a detrimental impact on the academic achievements of students. Education offers essential knowledge and skills, and the closure of schools deprives children and adolescents of chances for progress and advancement. Impoverished learners face more severe drawbacks, since they have limited opportunities for education beyond high school (Mitiku Demsew & Teferra, 2021). When schools shut down, caregivers are often expected to facilitate at-home learning for children and may encounter difficulties in fulfilling this duty. This particularly applies to guardians who lack educational or financial support (Dangwal & Dangwal, 2019). The closing of schools has a significant impact not only on students, teachers, and families but also has wide-ranging financial and cultural implications.

The pandemic-induced closure of schools has brought to light several societal and economic challenges, such as student loan burdens, access to higher-level education, inadequate access to food, homelessness, difficulties in accessing childcare, medical services, housing, internet, and disability support services (Davitt et al., 2021). The consequences were especially grave for children with disabilities and their families, resulting in interrupted education, diminished access to proper nutrition, childcare challenges, and financial burdens for families unable to work (Mitiku Demsew & Teferra, 2021).

Proper nutrition has a crucial role in the intellectual, cognitive, scholastic and academic development of children. A significant number of youngsters depend on complementary or restricted evening meals provided at school. The closure of schools has a detrimental impact on the nutritional well-being of children, especially those who rely on school-provided meals (McCary, 2006). The global ramifications on academic credibility have been widely noticed. Contract cheating, the act of outsourcing academic work to others, scholarly record sharing, the unauthorized distribution of academic materials, and test cheating, the act of dishonestly obtaining answers during exams, have all been recognized as significant concerns (Dawson, 2024). Several universities used business administration to oversee test administration, nevertheless, apprehensions promptly emerged about student security, surveillance, and the potential effects on student emotional welfare. Consequently, the utilization of commercial e-proctoring services led to a surge in student demonstrations throughout different nations (Dawson, 2024). The Education sector has seen many detrimental consequences as a result of the Coronavirus pandemic. These include a decline in

educational activity owing to the closure of schools, inadequate online learning due to unprepared instructors, and a fall in worldwide commercial prospects. In addition to these adverse effects, guardians have an augmented responsibility to motivate their wards in domains where only a limited number of skilled guardians can provide guidance (Sahu, 2020). Most students residing in rural and distant regions lack access to the internet or other digital resources necessary for efficient online education. The problem of delayed payment of fees is hindering the operations of establishments and producing distress among student guardians (Jena, P.K. 2020a).

Adopting Online Teaching and Learning: A Significant Opportunity

The prevailing epidemic has transformed the very conventional, lecture-based education approach into a novel and ambitious web-based innovation and technology. The disruptive impact on the provision of education is compelling politicians to devise strategies for implementing accountability on a large scale, while also providing comprehensive e-learning initiatives and managing sophisticated digital gadgets. Internet learning has facilitated the development of more efficient and advantageous acquisition of advanced skills and knowledge. Online education is the optimal choice during the ongoing epidemic (Jena, 2020). The legislature's computerized India vision is becoming an essential tool for understanding the present crisis caused by COVID-19. Technology-based training is unequivocally more direct in all aspects. Due to the looming pandemic dangers, the Indian legislature has implemented the closure of institutions and schools. Meanwhile, state governments and commercial entities have made efforts to engage in lawful actions. The Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) has implemented several initiatives, such as online platforms and educational channels through direct-to-home TV and Radio, to facilitate the ongoing education of pupils. Amidst the lockdown, individuals in the roles of understudies, scholars, and students are using popular online platforms to engage in remote teaching and learning. These platforms encompass Google Meets, WhatsApp, Zoom, Facebook Live, Telegram, YouTube Live, and others. To effectively address the issue and ultimately establish a robust education system in India, a comprehensive strategy including several strategies is necessary.

The Diksha platform offers customized digital or e-learning materials for instructors, students, and parents, including video tutorials, practice sheets, course materials, and evaluations. The material was developed collaboratively by over 250 educators proficient in several vernaculars, under the guidance of the National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT) and the Central Board of Secondary Education (CBSE). The application is also functional in offline mode. The platform offers a vast collection of more than 80,000 digital books specifically designed for students in grades 1 to 12. These books have been developed by CBSE and NCERT and are available in several languages. Aside from Diksha, other platforms, for example, the National Repository of Open Educational Resources (NROER) introduced a vast array of educational assets, including books, interactive modules, videos, and science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) based games, in various dialects for students and educators. Swayam Prabha is an online platform providing 1900 courses across all school subjects (classes 9-12) and higher education disciplines, including humanities, engineering, law, social sciences, and management. It operates 32 DTH TV channels broadcasting 24/7, available through a DD free dish set-top box and antenna. Postgraduate students can use e-PG Pathshala for online courses, digital books, and study tools, especially useful during lockdowns and public health emergencies (Jena, P.K., 2020a).

In addition, it is necessary to establish comprehensive educational programs, specifically targeting the most disadvantaged and marginalized individuals. Due to the increasing growth of Internet users in India, it is projected that 85% of nuclear families will have access to the Internet by 2024. This progress allows for widespread availability and customization of advice, even in the most distant areas of the nation. This has the potential to modify the coaching framework and enhance the appropriateness of learning and teaching by offering students and educators a range of alternatives to explore (Chopra et al., 2019). India's educational institutions have acknowledged the need and are diligently striving to provide regular support services to students during the pandemic. The epidemic has expedited the implementation of sophisticated educational advancements. Educational institutions transitioned to a blended learning methodology. It fostered a culture of enhanced creativity and profound perception among instructors and students. Educational institutions have shown a significant interest in using board frameworks

for instructional purposes. The use of digital versions of educational resources has seen a rise. Open and distance learning courses are highly sought for (Bal & Gupta, 2020).

DIFFICULTIES IN ADOPTING ONLINE TEACHING-LEARNING

The main challenges faced by both students and instructors in educational settings, despite their willingness to use digital and e-learning platforms, which encompass technical issues, interruptions, time management, maintaining motivation, understanding course expectations, lack of face-to-face interaction, adapting to technology, and uncertainty about the future (Andersson & Grönlund, 2009). Undoubtedly, isolated and undeveloped sections of the nation face a scarcity of essential e-learning elements, including personal computers, laptops, electricity, necessary skills, and active collaboration between students and teachers. The primary obstacle would likely include ensuring that certain requirements for e-learning, such as access to ICT devices and network infrastructure, are fulfilled. It is crucial to align the perspectives of instructors and students towards e-learning and persuade them to embrace it. Another factor to consider is the specific expertise of the personnel who will be involved in the e-learning program. Both parties agreed that a major problem was the absence of professionals to train them in using e-learning platforms and the inadequate preparation in using the technology (Aung & Khaing, 2016).

The expense associated with obtaining, overseeing, and upkeeping Information and communication technology infrastructure has been recognized as a substantial obstacle in the execution and assessment of e-learning by companies and academic institutions. Inadequate lecture room facilities and a shortage of electricity have hindered the planning and implementation of e-learning, especially in rural and isolated places. Furthermore, the lack of a robust e-learning educational program presents a significant barrier to the effective delivery and reception of e-learning. Another issue pertains to the course delivery method. The issue at hand pertains to whether or not understudies should have the freedom to choose the method by which material is presented to them.

Students with poor proficiency are less inclined to use e-learning due to a lack of confidence in comprehending English written resources. Based on a survey, the

overwhelming majority of participants saw language as a hindrance to e-learning. In addition to these notable challenges, additional key concerns include disruptions, effective time management, and maintaining motivation for learning (Chopra et al., 2019). There is a need to reconsider existing methods of teaching and learning in primary and higher education by carefully integrating classroom instruction with e-learning modalities to establish a cohesive educational system. The primary public concern is the seamless integration of emerging technologies into the existing Indian education system, which is unparalleled in its scale and size, including more than 15 million schools and 50,000 prestigious educational institutions.

COVID19'S IMPACT ON GIRLS' EDUCATION IN INDIA

Notwithstanding the many objections and concerns, it is evident that the enrollment of females in educational institutions is steadily rising. India's female literacy rate saw a significant improvement from 9% at the time of independence to 65% in 2011, owing to both individual and government initiatives. The female gross enrollment ratio in elementary schools saw a significant rise, surging from 61% in 1970 to 115% in 2015. The enrollment rate in secondary schools saw a significant rise, rising from 14% in 1970 to 75% in 2015. Regrettably, the COVID-19 pandemic has significantly disturbed this previously positive trend, and it seems probable that it will now go in the other direction. By July 22, 2020, a total of 282 million youngsters, with 134 million being females, experienced the impact of a countrywide shutdown of schools in 40 different nations. Stefania Giannini, a representative from UNESCO, voiced worry on the possibility of higher rates of students leaving school. This issue is particularly focused on teenage girls, as it might worsen the existing disparities between genders in education. Additionally, there is a heightened risk of early pregnancy, sexual exploitation, and forced marriage associated with this situation. The COVID-19 pandemic is anticipated to result in the withdrawal of around 10 million female students from secondary schools in India. This situation poses a threat to their physical, emotional, and academic well, and it also undoes the progress made in recent times. The repercussions of non-attendance at school are diverse and intensified particularly for female pupils.

YEAR	BOYS	GIRLS
1947	13,948,979	4,297,785

1942	12,226,311	3,726,876
1937	11,007,683	3,138,357
1932	10,273,888	2,492,649
1927	9,315,144	1,842,352
1922	6,962,928	1,424,422

Source: Government of India, Progress of Education in India

Due to the ongoing economic crisis, characterized by salary reductions and joblessness, it is anticipated that there will be adverse consequences for girls' education. Given the scarcity of resources, families may choose to prioritize the education of males over girls. Ample evidence is available from the 2014 Ebola epidemic in West Africa, which indicates that females discontinued their education as a result of heightened home caregiving obligations and a transition towards money production. Typically, boys were favored over girls in terms of access to education. The lessons derived from the Ebola crisis substantiate the notion that the collective efforts of non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and governments to facilitate girls' access to education may be rendered futile as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Before the COVID-19 pandemic, it was found that females who engaged in two hours of domestic chores daily had a reduced likelihood of completing their secondary education in the nation. Due to the societal taboo surrounding menstruation, females have been prevented from pursuing their education after reaching puberty. In India, where there is no provision for social security, the economic and social difficulties caused by COVID-19 would further intensify gender disparities in schooling.

A new research named 'Whatever she studies, she can't escape from washing dishes: Gender imbalance in secondary school,' reveals that girls' involvement in household tasks and domestic work responsibilities is the primary factor contributing to the disparity between genders in secondary education (Singh & Mukherjee, 2018).

Further data from the aforementioned research indicates that the involvement of children, particularly girls, in domestic chores is a major factor contributing to the significant gender disparity in secondary education, especially in Classes 10 and 9. A report introduced by the Indian division of Young Lives, a global research project on childhood poverty, shows that 358 boys (76.8%) and 322 girls (66.3%) from the survey group

successfully finished their secondary school. This data reveals a gender disparity of almost 10 percentage points. The study findings indicate that males who dedicated two hours per day to home chores had a completion rate of secondary school of 72.7%, while girls had a completion rate of 55%, resulting in a difference of 17.7 percentage points. In addition, a mere 40% of male students and 34% of female students who dedicated three or more hours to work managed to successfully complete Class 10. The highest proportion of male and female students who successfully finished secondary school was seen among those whose moms had attained elementary education, while the second highest proportion was found among those whose mothers had no formal education. Even in cases when moms had obtained a secondary education or pursued further studies, a disparity still existed. The research indicates that mothers' level of education contributes to 2.6% of the disparity between genders.

For several girls, especially those residing in rural regions, the noon meal supplied by schools becomes their only source of nourishment during the day. The Studies have shown that the midday meal program, implemented in 1995, has helped reduce the financial burden on families in providing nourishment to girls, therefore contributing to the narrowing of the gender gap in schooling. According to economists Dreze and Kingdon, providing mid-day meals boosts the chances of a girl finishing primary school by 30% and reduces the percentage of girls not enrolled in school by 50%. The interruption of schooling has significantly disrupted the mid-day meal program. If this incentive is not supplied, families may choose to remove their girls from school.

The Center for Global Development performed a comprehensive survey of 82 organizations representing a minimum of 32 nations, including South Asia. The primary results of this study will be published in May 2020. A primary worry, as reported by 56% of participants, is the vulnerability of girls to abuse and violence.

Based on the poll conducted by the Center for Global Development, 40% of participants hold the view that the closing of schools increases the likelihood of early marriage and childbearing among females. Due to heightened financial burdens within households and the closing of schools, parents are opting to arrange early marriages for their daughters, especially when dowry payments are at stake, or girls may be coerced into

engaging in transactional sexual relationships. Previous data indicates that there was an increase in adolescent pregnancies during the Ebola pandemic.

To sustain the progress of education, several institutions have implemented virtual classrooms. Upon the first use of information technology in education more than twenty years ago, there were optimistic expectations that it would enhance the accessibility of education for disadvantaged individuals. Nevertheless, this anticipated outcome has not materialized, and the digital gap has instead expanded at a fast pace, resulting in direct repercussions. According to A Mukhopadhyay of the Indian Statistical Institute, using data from the part of the survey of Education in 2014, the Internet is only accessible to 27% of Indian homes.

Consequently, a mere 12.5% of Indian families possess access to internet services inside their residences. Mukhopadhyay argues that it is crucial to acknowledge the distinction between home internet access and general internet access, especially in the current moment when students are restricted to their homes owing to the lockdown. The source of this information is The Print, dated April 9, 2020. Delivering virtual instruction to kids during the COVID-19 pandemic has been a considerable obstacle. For instance, whereas over 85% of university students from urban families had internet connectivity, just 41% are expected to have access to it in their homes. Merely 28% of pupils hailing from rural homes are inclined to possess access to the internet in their residences. Based on the National Sample Survey 2017-18, online courses do not address the digital disparity in the nation, since just 16% of females have access to the internet compared to 36% of men. The existence of this divide may lead to severe outcomes, as seen in Kerala, where a 14-year-old student with exceptional academic abilities took her own life due to her inability to attend her virtual lessons.

CONCLUSION

India is a large and diverse country characterized by a high population density. The nationwide lockdown was the major approach in combating the COVID-19 pandemic, commence on March 25, 2020, and has led to significant changes in the global education system. Its impacts have created an opportunity to restructure school education. The COVID-19 pandemic has brought about substantial changes in the educational scenario in India. accelerating the integration of e-learning and digital platforms into the mainstream curriculum. The nationwide lockdown initiated on March 25, 2020,

forced educational institutions to rapidly adopt online teaching methods, which helped preserve academic continuity during an unprecedented disruption. This shift has underscored the potential of digital learning to enhance educational accessibility and flexibility. Computerized learning has been the preferred approach for professionals seeking to enhance their skills in a more automated society, and e-learning has been included in the curricula of schools and universities during the lockdown to preserve academic continuity. However, the rapid transition to online education has also revealed substantial challenges, particularly the digital divide that affects economically disadvantaged students who lack reliable internet access and smart devices. Additionally, the preparedness of educators and the availability of digital resources have emerged as critical factors influencing the effectiveness of online education.

The NEP (New Education Policy) 2020 aims to leverage the benefits of sophisticated and online education while addressing its limitations. Initiatives such as competency-based learning, virtual laboratories, and pilot studies are steps towards creating a more resilient and inclusive education system. Continuous assessment and flexible approaches to teaching and learning will be essential to ensure that all students can benefit from these advancements. While the pandemic has presented significant challenges while also offering an opportunity to reconsider and reform the Indian education system. By building on the lessons learned and addressing the disparities exposed, India can develop a more robust and equitable educational framework for the future.

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NU, DP, PCO, NV, SKS & SKS was responsible for the first manuscript draft. All authors contributed to subsequent drafts and approved the final version.

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Availability of data and materials

No datasets were generated or analysed during the current study

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Not applicable.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests

REFERENCES

1. Wickham, B. (2019). The school education system in India. *Education Today*, July, Issue.
2. Alvi, M., Gupta, M. (2020). Learning in times of lockdown: how Covid-19 is affecting education and food security in India. *Food Sec*, 12(4), 793–796, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12571-020-01065-4>.
3. Kapasia, N., Paul, P., Roy, A., Saha, J., Zaveri, A., Mallick, R., Barman, B., Das, P., & Chouhan, P. (2020b). Impact of lockdown on learning status of undergraduate and postgraduate students during COVID-19 pandemic in West Bengal, India. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 116, 105194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chilyouth.2020.105194>
4. Jena, P. K. (2020, May 31). *Online Learning during Lockdown Period for COVID-19 in India*. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3691545
5. A. Khattar, P. R. Jain and S. M. K. Quadri, “Effects of the Disastrous Pandemic COVID 19 on Learning Styles, Activities and Mental Health of Young Indian Students - A Machine Learning Approach,” 2020 4th International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control Systems (ICICCS), Madurai, India, 2020, pp. 1190-1195, doi: 10.1109/ICICCS48265.2020.9120955.
6. Gomez, E., Azadi, J., & Magid, D. (2020). Innovation born in Isolation: Rapid transformation of an In-Person medical student radiology elective to a remote learning experience during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Academic Radiology*, 27(9), 1285–1290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acra.2020.06.001>
7. UNESCO. (2020). *National education responses to COVID-19: Summary report of UNESCO's online survey* (ED/PLS/EDP/2020/03).

8. Barrett, S. (2020, March 23). *Coronavirus on campus: College students scramble to solve food insecurity and housing challenges*. CNBC. <https://www.cnbc.com/2020/03/23/coronavirus-on-campus-students-face-food-insecurity-housing-crunch.html>
9. McCary, J. (2006). Improving access to school-based nutrition services for children with special health care needs. *Journal of the American Dietetic Association*, 106(9), 1333-1336. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jada.2006.07.022>
10. Appiah, K.A. (2020). If my classmates are going to cheat on an online exam, Why can't I? New York Times.
11. *E-Proctoring: Understanding the debate about invigilating remote exams*. (2020, June 8). Learning, Teaching and Leadership. <https://drsaraheaton.wordpress.com/2020/05/12/e-proctoring-understanding-the-debate-about-invigilating-remote-exams/>
12. Sahu, P. (2020). Closure of Universities due to coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19): Impact on education and mental health of students and academic staff. *Curçus*. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.7541>
13. ET Government & www.ETGovernment.com. (2020, April 16). COVID-19 Pandemic: Impact and strategies for the education sector in India. *ETGovernment.com*. <https://government.economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/education/covid-19-pandemic-impact-and-strategies-for-education-sector-in-india/75173099>
14. Uthale, I. A., Dalvi, Y., & KLE Society's Science & Commerce College, Kalamboli, Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra, India. (2022). Impact of National Education Policy 2020 (NEP) on higher education in Covid pandemic. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Communication and Technology (IJARSCT)*, 2(5), 79–81. <https://doi.org/10.48175/IJARSCT-3564>
15. Chopra, G., Madan, P., Jaisingh, P., & Bhaskar, P. (2019). Effectiveness of e-learning portal from students' perspective: A structural equation model (SEM) approach. *Interactive Technology and Smart Education*, 16. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ITSE-05-2018-0027>
16. Al, S. B. G. E. (2020b, February 2). *Technology and E-Learning in Higher education*. <http://sersc.org/journals/index.php/IJAST/article/view/5185>
17. Andersson, A., & Grönlund, Å. (2009). A Conceptual Framework for E Learning in Developing Countries: A Critical Review of Research challenges. *The Electronic Journal on Information Systems in Developing Countries*, 38(1), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1681-4835.2009.tb00271.x>
18. Aung, T. N., & Khaing, S. S. (2015). Challenges of Implementing e-Learning in Developing Countries: A review. *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, 405–411. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-23207-2_41
19. 'Whatever she may study, she can't escape from washing dishes': gender inequity in secondary education – evidence from a longitudinal study in India | *Young Lives*. (2017, April 28). <https://www.younglives.org.uk/publications/whatever-she-may-study-she-cant-escape-washing-dishes-gender-inequity-secondary#:~:text=Decomposition%20analysis%20highlights%20that%20engaging,by%20the%20qualitative%20case%20studies>
20. Mishra, D. (2020). Web-based education: history and scope in India. *Lkouniv*. https://www.academia.edu/43325346/Web_based_Education_History_and_Scope_in_India